

Deep Reinforcement Learning for Improving Competitive Cycling Performance

Giorgos Demosthenous^a, Marios Kyriakou^{a,b} and Vassilis Vassiliades^{a,*}

^a*CYENS Centre of Excellence, Dimarchias Square 23, Nicosia 1016, Cyprus*

^b*Mirror 3D Lab Ltd, Ayiou Pavlou 63B, Nicosia 1107, Cyprus*

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
reinforcement learning
recommendation systems
competitive cycling

ABSTRACT

Developing expert systems that make use of artificial intelligence (AI) to provide predictive analytics as well as targeted recommendations for decision support has been gaining momentum in recent years. Both academia and industry are looking into creating such systems to solve real-world problems and tackle specific challenges. In our work, we investigate the potential application of different machine learning approaches to solutions around competitive cycling. Specifically, we build and evaluate prediction models that are capable of accurately predicting a cyclist's speed and heart rate using sensory information collected during bike rides. In addition, we create a recommendation module that is able to provide real-time action suggestions to cyclists regarding their posture with the goal of improving their overall performance. We achieve this using a combination of model-based reinforcement learning (RL) and deep RL. In particular, we use model-based RL to learn a "simulator" of bike rides using the prediction models and action profiles extracted from sensors placed on the cyclists' back. We then use deep Q-learning in the simulator to extract policies that improve a cyclist's behavior during a bike ride. Our evaluation shows that by recommending specific actions throughout the ride, cyclists can increase their overall average speed with only a minimal impact on their heart rate. The results presented in this paper constitute clear evidence that advanced AI techniques are a prime candidate for further developing intelligent solutions in competitive cycling and other similar areas.

1. Introduction

The rapid advances in artificial intelligence (AI) in the last couple of decades have led to an explosion of new applications around recommendation and decision support systems, predictive analytics, forecasting and other adjacent areas. Devising novel approaches and incorporating them into expert systems for solving real-world problems has been a major drive for academia as well as industry (Sahin et al., 2012). Such systems are being used in a variety of domains with promising results. In health, machine learning has been used for estimating energy expenditure in real-time (Munguia Tapia, 2008) to help fight obesity and other activity related health threats, and for creating highly accurate predictors of non-exercise VO₂max (Akay et al., 2009). In finance, deep reinforcement learning (RL) has been used for algorithmic trading (Théate and Ernst, 2021) with results surpassing benchmark strategies, and for portfolio management (Soleymani and Paquet, 2021) with frameworks adjusting the investment policy. Recommendation and decision support systems find many applications in agriculture, where machine learning is used to provide valuable suggestions and insight to farmers regarding crop, livestock, soil and water management (Liakos et al., 2018). Predictive models have also found applications in sports where for example, neural networks have been used to predict the performance

of athletes to help with the cricket team selection (Iyer and Sharda, 2009), or where support vector machines have been incorporated to predict an athlete's aerobic fitness (Acikkar et al., 2009). Creating intelligent systems that are able to provide high-quality and real-time action suggestions with the main objective of improving overall performance, is also another research area that has been gaining momentum in recent years. In (Liu et al., 2014) for example, a system using genetic algorithms has been developed for providing real-time recommendations to tourists with the goal of personalizing their experience, avoiding traffic jams and reducing the overall visiting time.

In our project, we seek to create an advanced recommendation module that is able to improve the performance of competitive cyclists by providing real-time action suggestions. Throughout a bike ride, cyclists are expected to perform at the maximum average speed they can. A major element that affects their overall performance is their posture during the ride, where having an aerodynamic position is of grave importance (Crouch et al., 2017). Being able to accurately predict a cyclist's speed in real-time using posture and other sensory information while riding is also desirable in competitive cycling, since it helps improve both indoor and outdoor training sessions. In this work, as seen in Figure 1, we use data collected from sensors placed on cyclists to investigate which attributes contribute the most in predicting their speed throughout a ride. Using this information, we are able to create highly accurate models for predicting a cyclist's speed in real time, as well as other important variables such as heart rate. We then use these models as the basis

*Corresponding author

✉ g.demosthenous@cyens.org.cy (G. Demosthenous);
m.kyriakou@cyens.org.cy (M. Kyriakou); v.vassiliades@cyens.org.cy (V. Vassiliades)

ORCID(s): 0000-0002-1804-6686 (G. Demosthenous);
0000-0001-8445-5990 (M. Kyriakou); 0000-0002-1336-5629 (V. Vassiliades)

Figure 1: The project structure and workflow.

for creating a recommendation module that provides real-time suggestions to the cyclists on how they can change their posture during the ride to improve their overall performance. As we present in this paper, our module is able to improve the average speed of all the cyclists from whom the data is collected, with only a minimal impact on their average heart rate during the ride.

This paper is organized as follows: First, we discuss previous work on RL approaches and other relevant topics in Section 2. In Section 3, we describe the dataset used for our work, as well as the feature engineering and selection process. Section 4 shows the regression algorithms that were developed and evaluated in order to come up with the final prediction model. In Section 5, we present in detail how the recommendation module was built, as well as how it performs under a simulated environment. In addition, we provide a brief evaluation of our module in the real-world. Finally, in Section 6 we draw our conclusions and discuss about possible future work.

2. Background

In this section, we briefly discuss some of the technologies and general approaches used in the context of this project. The three main parts of our work are: (1) the feature vector, (2) the prediction model and (3) the recommendation module.

The first step in creating robust and accurate machine learning models, is usually the engineering of a feature vector that encapsulates highly relevant information in regard to the problem that is being tackled. In (Heaton, 2016), a variety of possible feature types are presented like polynomials, powers, differences and ratios, some of which are used in our work as well. To create our prediction model, we go beyond simple linear regression approaches. When it comes to using regression for predictions, decision-tree-based methods like stochastic gradient boosting and random forests tend to perform extremely well (Friedman, 2002; Segal, 2004). In time series forecasting, neural networks have been shown to perform significantly better than traditional or other regression-based methods (Hill et al., 1996). Another approach for the prediction model is symbolic regression, a genetic programming-based method (Koza, 1992) that has comparable performance with other state-of-the-art algorithms and the advantage of finding a simple formula that governs the data, but at the disadvantage of extremely slow training times (Orzechowski et al., 2018).

2.1. Reinforcement Learning Preliminaries

RL can be used to solve problems modelled as Markov Decision Processes (MDPs). An MDP is a tuple (S, A, T, R) where S is a set of states and $s_t \in S$ is the state the agent is in at time t , A is a set of actions and $a_t \in A$ is the action the agent chooses at time t , $T : S \times A \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the transition function where $T(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1})$ gives the probability of arriving in state s_{t+1} when choosing action a_t in state s_t , and $r : S \times A \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the immediate reward function with $r(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1})$ being the reward the agent receives when choosing action a_t in state s_t and arriving in state s_{t+1} .

The agent's goal is to learn an action selection policy $\pi : S \times A \rightarrow [0, 1]$, such that $\sum_a \pi(a_t | s_t) = 1$ where $\pi(a_t | s_t)$ is the probability of choosing action a_t in state s_t , that optimizes the discounted return: $V^\pi(s_t) = r_t^\pi + \gamma r_{t+1}^\pi + \gamma^2 r_{t+2}^\pi + \dots = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \gamma^i r_{t+i}^\pi$, where $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ is a discount factor, $r_t^\pi = r(s_t, \pi(a_t | s_t), s_{t+1})$ and $V^\pi(s)$ is also known as the value of state s under policy π . An optimal policy is one that maximizes the discounted return from any state, i.e., $\forall s \in S : \pi^* = \arg \max_\pi V^\pi(s)$.

T and r are collectively known as the “model” of the environment which can be exploited by planning methods to optimize behavior. In particular, the value function of the optimal policy will have the following property:

$$V^*(s) = \max_a \sum_{s'} T(s, a, s')(r(s, a, s') + \gamma V^*(s'))$$

and $V^*(s) = \max_a Q^*(s, a)$ where Q^* is the optimal state-action value function.

In the RL setting, however, the model (T and r) is not known apriori, thus, the agent needs to interact with the environment to learn the optimal policy. There are two general approaches for doing so: model-free and model-based methods.

2.1.1. Model-free RL

Model-free methods assume that an agent can repeatedly interact with the environment and sample the state transitions and rewards in order to discover the best actions in each state. This can be done by learning either a value function from which the optimal policy can be derived, or the policy itself (i.e., policy search methods). Q-learning (Watkins and Dayan, 1992) is a popular example of a value function-based method which uses the following update equation:

$$Q_{t+1}(s_t, a_t) = Q_t(s_t, a_t) + \alpha_t \delta_t$$

where $\delta_t = r_t^\pi + \gamma \max_a Q_t(s_{t+1}, a) - Q_t(s_t, a_t)$ is the temporal difference (TD) error (an error between a target and the current value), and $0 \leq \alpha_t \leq 1$ is a step size parameter. This algorithm is an example of off-policy learning, meaning that the agent can select actions with policy π , but learn a different policy - in particular the optimal one, as it updates the Q function towards the optimal values. When the Q function is stored in a table, the update above will converge to the optimal policy under certain conditions (Watkins and Dayan, 1992).

Model-free algorithms typically explore new samples through randomized exploration, either in action space or in parameter space (in some instances of policy search). This randomized exploration, however, is both sample-inefficient and potentially unsafe, which hinders the applicability of such methods to real-world systems. For instance, a human cannot be engaged for thousands of hours in order for the machine to learn some useful policy. Similarly, a robot cannot try “wildly” random actions to explore various possibilities, as many of them will lead to damages.

2.1.2. Model-based RL

A way to address the aforementioned practical problems is through the use of a simulated environment, rather than interacting with the real-world. Model-based RL (e.g., see Hester and Stone, 2012; Chatzilygeroudis et al., 2019) attempts to learn the model (T and r) of the environment and use it to plan optimal actions or learn a near-optimal policy. In essence, this model acts as a simulator of the real-world system, which can be executed much faster than real-time for the purposes of learning or planning.

In this project, we follow a model-based approach to learn a simulator of bike rides from collected data. This permits the use of exploration inside the model to discover actions that deviate from the ones chosen in each state by the cyclist, which result in better performance.

2.1.3. Deep RL

When the problem has a continuous state space, function approximation needs to be employed in order to provide generalization between similar states. However, the traditional Q-learning algorithm is known to diverge with function approximation (Tsitsiklis and Van Roy, 1997). The Deep Q-learning algorithm (Mnih et al., 2015) uses a deep neural network to approximate the Q function and has empirically shown to mitigate the problem of divergence. This was

achieved through the introduction of two mechanisms: (1) storing previous experience tuples (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in a dataset and applying Q-learning updates on samples drawn uniformly from it, and (2) a copy of the network that computes the TD-error’s target Q values, is held fixed between updates and is replaced by the Q network periodically. The resulting deep Q network (DQN) agent was able to learn to play Atari games from pixels and has sparked the field of deep RL.

Deep RL (DRL) has been used to solve problems or tackle specific challenges in a plethora of areas ranging from gaming to healthcare. In (Silver et al., 2016), AlphaGo using deep neural networks and tree search, managed to defeat for the first time ever the world champion in the game of Go. In healthcare, DRL is being used to create dynamic treatment regimes to aid doctors in giving more targeted, patient-specific recommendations (Liu et al., 2017).

In recommendation systems, RL is commonly used for personalized news recommendations (Li et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2018). In our work, we build the recommendation module using DQN to tackle the challenge of providing real-time suggestions to cyclists. While state-of-the-art DRL algorithms provide significant improvements over DQN (e.g., see Rainbow: (Hessel et al., 2018); TD3: (Fujimoto et al., 2018); PPO: (Schulman et al., 2017); SAC: (Haarnoja et al., 2018)), in this project we use vanilla DQN due to being well-tested and easy to use and experiment with when using libraries such as TF-Agents¹ (Guadarrama et al., 2018).

3. Dataset and Feature Engineering

In this section we describe the dataset that is used throughout this project, as well as how the raw data is collected. We also talk about how the features necessary to train our models are created and which ones are finally selected.

3.1. Dataset Description

The dataset consists of 14 different bicycle rides each containing timeseries data which are recorded every second. The duration of each ride varies from 10 minutes (shortest ride) up to 3.3 hours (longest ride). The data was recorded from 7 individual male bicyclists with an average age of 43 years (40 to 48), an average height of 178.14 cm (177 to 179) and an average weight of 78.43 kg (70 to 90). Two types of bikes are found in the dataset: Triathlon and Road bikes. The bike weights range from 7 kg to 10kg with an average of 9.29 kg. Raw measurements are recorded for the duration of a ride using information from sensors placed on the cyclists. Specifically, two inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensors are placed on the lower (BackSensor1) and upper (BackSensor2) back of the cyclists to capture and calculate data related to their position and stability. Other sensory information is recorded through smart devices and is used to calculate variables such as heart rate, speed and others. The full list of the raw measurements along with

¹See: https://www.tensorflow.org/agents/tutorials/1_dqn_tutorial. Last accessed 12 Dec 2021.

Table 1
List of all raw measurements recorded during a ride.

Measurements	Description	Measurements	Description
Good Position	Is the position in the “right good boundaries” ? (Yes/No)	∴	∴
BackSensor1 Position	Depending on the Bike Type, the calibration of BackSensor1 Roll angle and the current BackSensor1 Roll angle	BackSensor2 Roll	0 – 90 degrees
BackSensor2 Position	Depending on the Bike Type, the calibration of BackSensor2 Roll angle and the current BackSensor2 roll angle	Power	The current power from the cyclist (watt)
Overall Stability	Steady/Moderate/Unstable depending on BackSensor1 and BackSensor2 Pitch Calibration and current angles	Speed	The current speed of the cyclist (kmh)
BackSensor1 Stability	Steady/Moderate/Unstable depending on BackSensor1 Pitch values	Distance	The distance covered so far in the ride (km)
BackSensor2 Stability	Steady/Moderate/Unstable depending on BackSensor2 Pitch values	Inclination	The road inclination
BackSensor1 Pitch	0 – 90 degrees	Altitude	The current altitude of the cyclist
BackSensor2 Pitch	0 – 90 degrees	Longitude	The current longitude of the cyclist
BackSensor1 Roll	0 – 90 degrees	Latitude	The current latitude of the cyclist
∴	∴	Balance Left	The bike balance measured from the left pedal (0 – 100%)
		Balance Right	The bike balance measure from the right pedal (0 – 100%)
		Cadence	The rate at which a cyclist pedals (RPM)
		Heart Rate	The heart rate of the cyclist (bpm)
		Elapsed Time	The time elapsed so far in the ride (seconds)

their brief description can be seen in Table 1. Before the ride begins, bicyclists manually enter some information such as their Functional Threshold Power (FTP), which is the average number of watts a rider can sustain in an hour, and their Lactate Threshold Heart Rate (LTHR), which is the average heart rate during a sustained, maximal, one-hour effort. These values are estimated by the bicyclists themselves in a lab or through guided tests with the help of a power meter. The FTP entries in the dataset range from 220 to 317 with an average of 260.14, and the LTHR entries range from 151 to 173 with an average of 161.43. The two sensors that capture positional information are also calibrated to the current position of the bicyclist.

For the purpose of this project, we do not require predictions or recommendations to take place every second, therefore reducing the granularity of the dataset is desirable. For this reason, we scale down the timeseries recordings to every 5 seconds (granularity=5) and we use the average of each measurement for that duration instead. For clarity, we refer to every 5-second block as a timestep.

3.2. Feature Engineering

In order for our regression models to achieve the highest possible accuracy and robustness, we first need to create and select features that contribute the most to the correct prediction of a cyclist’s speed. For this reason, we investigate

a variety of feature types for all available ride measurements. To create some of the features, we take into account raw measurements from the immediate past, for a specific window of timesteps, which we call the training window (TW). All the different feature types we experimented with are the following:

- **Raw:** The raw values of specified measurements at the current timestep.
- **Moving Averages (MA):** The average value of raw measurements in the last TW timesteps.
- **Accelerations (ACC):** The rate of change of a raw measurement between now and TW timesteps back.
- **Bivariate Features (a X b):** The product of two separate raw measurement features.
- **Polynomial Features (POLY):** Created by raising a specific raw measurement to the 3rd power.
- **Calibration Features (ACalDif):** Created by calculating the absolute difference between the current value of a raw measurement and their initial value during the calibration of the bike.

Before we proceed with creating new features, we need to see how each type of raw measurement correlates with

Figure 2: Correlation of raw measurements with speed.

the speed of a cyclist. This gives us a first insight to which ones could provide the most valuable information for speed prediction, and therefore focus on creating more complex features based on them. For example, as seen in Figure 2, the Longitude and Latitude of the cyclist have practically zero correlation with speed, and since this is something that was intuitively expected, they are not worth investigating any further.

In addition to correlation with speed, we export the importance score of each feature by using Breiman and Friedman’s methodology (Breiman et al., 2017), as it was implemented by Scikit-Learn through their Random Forests regressor (Pedregosa et al., 2011). We gradually introduce each type of feature and discard those that have close to zero correlation with speed and at the same time have a low importance score. Our final feature vector consists of 25 features selected based on the aforementioned criteria. The correlation of the selected features with speed can be seen in Figure 3. The importance score of all the features adds up to one and can be seen in Figure 4. With the exception of Accelerations, where the features did not seem to have a high contribution potential, all other feature types are present in the final selection. All features are normalized using zero-mean normalization.

4. Prediction Models

One of the main objectives of this project is to create prediction models that are able to accurately estimate and predict the cyclist’s speed or any other target variables when required (e.g., heart rate). For this reason, a selection of regression models is built, fine-tuned and evaluated using machine learning libraries such as TensorFlow, Scikit-Learn and Fastr. The best performing regressor is kept as our final prediction model and is later integrated to the recommendation module described in Section 5.

4.1. Regression Models

To come up with our final prediction model, we experiment with different types or implementations of regressors. We finetune the hyperparameters of each regressor by running model selection experiments (see Appendix A) and selecting the best performing settings. The selected models are the following:

- **Normal Linear Regression (NLR) – Scikit-Learn:** Linear Regression using the Normal Equation (closed-form solution), as implemented by Scikit-Learn, which is known for being able to train and perform predictions extremely fast when the number of features and data points is small. For this reason, we use and evaluate this model under a variety of different scenarios without any changes to the default model.
- **Gradient Descent Linear Regression (GDLR) – TensorFlow:** GDLR is built using a single fully connected (Dense) layer with only one neuron. It uses gradient descent and specifically, the Adam (Kingma and Ba, 2015) optimizer, where (after finetuning experiments) the learning rate is set to 0.001. Early stopping is incorporated during the training of the regressor, using 20% of the validation set. This model is included to show the impact of early stopping, as NLR does not use the validation set.
- **Neural Network (NN) – TensorFlow:** NN is built using a fully connected (Dense) layer with 16 neurons and a sigmoid activation function, followed by a Dropout layer (dropout percentage set to 30%) and another fully connected layer with a single neuron as the output. It uses the Adam optimizer, and the learning rate was set to 0.001. All aforementioned hyperparameters were set after extensive finetuning experiments. Early stopping is incorporated during the training of the regressor, using 20% of the validation set.
- **Gradient Boosting Decision Trees (GBDT) – Scikit-Learn:** The gradient boosting regressors is set to 200 estimators and a learning rate equal to 0.01.
- **Random Forests (RF) – Scikit-Learn:** The random forest regressor is set to 100 estimators.
- **Symbolic Regression – Fastr:** We also investigate Symbolic Regression, as implemented in the Fastr library², with different generation and population sizes to see whether it can be used to create an accurate model that is able to execute real-time inference.

4.2. Evaluation

In this section we present the methodology incorporated for the evaluation of the regression models and explain how the corresponding training, validation and testing sets are

²<https://github.com/cfusting/fast-symbolic-regression>. Last accessed 12 Dec 2021.

Deep RL for Improving Competitive Cycling Performance

Figure 3: Correlations of all selected features with speed.

created. We discuss the performance of each regressor and compare them to each other based on their Mean Absolute Error (MAE). Finally, we decide which regressor to use as our prediction model and therefore integrate to the recommendation module.

4.2.1. Methods

To evaluate the performance of all the regressor models, we incorporated two different methods: The Per Bike Ride Cross Validation, which is our main evaluation method, and the All Bike Rides Cross Validation (see Appendix B). The raw data from all bike rides is used to create individual samples, which are later distributed to training and validation sets based on the evaluation methodology being used. An individual sample consists of a feature vector created using a training window of 3 timesteps, and a target variable (e.g., speed) the value of which comes from the immediate next timestep. In the **Per Bike Ride Cross Validation** method, 11 out of the 12 bike rides are used to create samples for the training set, whereas the remaining ride is used to create samples for the validation set. The process is repeated 12 times, each with a different ride selected for validation in a round-robin fashion as seen in Figure 5. The Average MAE of all iterations is used to evaluate the performance of the regression models. The number of samples in the training and validation sets when each ride is selected for validation can be seen in Table 2. This methodology was devised to test the regressor’s ability to generalize since it allows us to stress-test the model on more realistic conditions, where new

data from a previously unseen cyclist have not yet been used in any retraining or personalization process.

Table 2

The number of samples in the training and validation sets when each ride is selected for validation.

Validation Ride	Training samples	Validation samples
1	16983	2135
2	16996	2122
3	17150	1968
4	17163	1955
5	17071	2047
6	18995	123
7	18473	645
8	16988	2130
9	18401	717
10	18064	1054
11	17078	2040
12	16936	2182

4.2.2. Results

To evaluate our models, we use 12 out of 14 bike rides available. Since the final trained prediction model is later integrated to our recommendation module (Section 5), we completely remove the remaining 2 rides (test set) from the dataset with the purpose of using them to evaluate the module on previously unseen bike rides as well.

Figure 4: The ranked importance of each selected feature for the prediction model.

Figure 5: Per Bike Ride Cross Validation

Per Bike Ride Cross Validation

We test the performance of all the regressors using the Per Bike Ride Cross Validation method, the results of which can be seen in in Table 3. We begin by comparing the two simple linear regression approaches, NLR and GDLR. Scikit Learn’s default implementation (NLR), has the advantage of training a lot faster than the GDLR we have built. GDLR on the other hand achieves a much smaller average MAE of 4.62 compared to the 6.27 by NLR. We then proceed to test the more advanced, neural-network-based approaches. NN achieves an average MAE of 4.24, a major improvement from the previous two regressors, but with the disadvantage of added training time. The two tree-based approaches, GBDT and RF, achieve an average MAE of 4.59 and 4.34 respectively. The RF regressor achieves an average MAE close to that of NN, but since it is not gradient based it has a much faster training time. We finally experiment with Symbolic Regression with the goal of exporting a compact

formula that would enable the model to perform real-time inference. The different combinations of increasing generation number and population size, visible in Table 4, show a gradual decrease in the average MAE of the model. When 6000 generations are used with a population of 600, it takes more than a day to train on our machine³, compared to a few minutes required by the rest of the regressors. Experimenting with higher generation and population sizes would require days of training, without significant, if any, improvement in performance. Therefore the increased performance potential of symbolic regression does not justify the added time cost in our situation.

Table 3

The average mean-absolute-error of each prediction model under the Per Bike Ride Cross Validation evaluation method (ranked in increasing order).

Model	Average MAE
Neural Network (NN)	4.24
Random Forests (RF)	4.34
Gradient Boosting Decision Trees (GBDT)	4.59
Gradient Descent Linear Regression (GDLR)	4.62
Symbolic Regression	4.86
Normal Linear Regression (NLR)	6.27

After reviewing the performance of all the regressors, we see that RF and NN have the lowest average MAE.

³We use a workstation with an Intel i7-8700K CPU, 32GB RAM, and an Nvidia RTX 2080 Ti GPU.

Table 4

The average mean-absolute-error of the Symbolic Regression model for different number of generations and population size pairs.

Generations	Population	Average MAE
500	250	6.03
1500	400	5.21
3000	500	4.86
6000	600	4.99

Since the selected prediction model is going to be integrated to the recommendation module, inference time is also extremely important. During evaluation, RF achieved an average inference time of 24 ms whereas NN performed worse with an average inference time of 36 ms. The fact that RF has faster training and inference times than NN with only a minor difference in average MAE (0.1 kmh), has led us to the decision of choosing RF as the most suitable regressor to be integrated to the recommendation module as the predictor element (Section 5.1). We denote as f_t^{speed} the speed prediction as produced by the model at time t .

5. Recommendation Module

In this section we present the recommendation module created with the goal of providing real-time suggestions to the cyclists to help increase their average speed for the duration of the ride whilst having a minimal impact on their average heart rate. We describe how RL is used in combination with our prediction model to create this recommendation module, and then proceed to run simulations in order to evaluate its performance. In addition, we provide a brief evaluation of our module in the real-world.

5.1. Environment

To build, train and test our reinforcement learning model we need to create a custom environment that closely resembles real-world bike rides. For this reason, we use the data from 12 pre-recorded bike rides to create the observations of the model at each time step. The agent in the model then uses these observations to take an action and create the next state. Based on the state of the agent at each time step, the environment gives the appropriate reward which allows for the model to train and learn the optimal observation-action pair. The goal of the agent is to optimize the ride's average speed without straining the cyclist. During training, the learning agent goes through all available rides, step-by-step, to create the states, take actions and learn based on the reward. Each episode ends when a bike ride has been parsed.

5.1.1. Actions

The suggestions provided to the cyclists are in regard to their angular position on the bike and change based on the state they are currently in. Therefore, suggestions are given in terms of BackSensor2-roll *changes*, i.e., difference between the value at time $t + 1$ and the value at time t .

Each timestep, the agent can choose among three actions: increase, decrease and steady.

When the BackSensor2-roll change is between -3 and 3 degrees, it is considered as a steady action. When the increase or decrease actions are taken, the BackSensor2-roll change lies in the ranges of [3,20] and [-3,-20] degrees respectively. After the action is selected from the agent, the exact degrees of BackSensor2-roll change corresponding to the action must be determined. For this reason, we estimate the distributions for the three possible actions from our dataset, prior to training, using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) with a Gaussian kernel. The distribution of each possible action can be seen in Figure 6. For each action selected by the agent, the BackSensor2-roll change is a continuous value sampled from the corresponding action distribution.

5.1.2. Observations

The same 25-feature vector exported for our prediction model, is used to create the state of the environment at each timestep. To create the agent's observations, some features need to be recalculated or estimated based on the action taken at the current timestep. Specifically, the BackSensor1 roll and heart rate features need to be estimated. To achieve this, we train two additional regressor models for each corresponding feature. To train the BackSensor1 roll regressor, we remove the following features from the 25-feature vector: *BackSensor1 Position*, *BackSensor1 Roll (degrees)*, *BackSensor1 Roll (degrees) (MA)*, *BackSensor1 Roll (degrees)xBackSensor2 Roll (degrees)*, *Inclination (%)xBackSensor1 Roll (degrees)*, *BackSensor1 Roll (degrees) (POLY)*, *BackSensor1 Roll (degrees) (ACalDif)*. To train the heart rate regressor, we keep the same 25-feature vector with the only difference that we now calculate the *Heart Rate (bpm) (ACalDif)* feature based on the previously estimated heart rate instead. Both regressors perform extremely well under the Per Bike Ride Cross Validation method, with an average MAE of 7.18 (bpm) for the heart rate predictor and 3.61 (degrees) for the BackSensor1 roll predictor. We use the new BackSensor2 roll (changed by action) and the new BackSensor1 roll (estimated) to recalculate all positional features that are affected by these changes. We denote as f_t^{hr} the heart rate prediction as produced by the model at time t .

5.1.3. Rewards

The goal of the learning agent is to optimize the ride's average speed without straining the cyclist. To improve the overall speed, the reward function must take into account the current speed of the cyclist, estimated by our prediction model, after the latest action. To limit the impact each action has on the cyclist's heart rate, an *action penalty*, p_t^{action} , of -1 is introduced into the reward function and is applied every time the agent decides to take an increase or decrease action. Our objective is to maximize speed, while minimizing both the heart rate and the number of increase/decrease actions. Therefore, the following reward function was adopted:

$$r_t = a \log(1 + f_t^{speed}) - b \log(1 + f_t^{hr}) - c p_t^{action}$$

Figure 6: The distributions being used to sample a continuous value when each corresponding action is selected. These were estimated from the dataset using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) with a Gaussian kernel. The sampled value (stochastic action) reflects a difference rather than the exact value, therefore, it is added on the BackSensor2 roll of the current timestep.

where $a, b, c \geq 0$ are (positive) weights to account for different tradeoffs, and

$$p_t^{action} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a_t \in \{\text{increase, decrease}\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The log-transformation is used to bring the speed and heart rate predictions to roughly the same order of magnitude as the action penalty. In our preliminary experiments, we found that using $a = c = 1$ and $b = 0$, that is a balance between maximizing speed and steady actions, was sufficient to produce improvements in all bike rides of the dataset, while having a minimal impact on the heart rate. Thus, the final, simplified reward function to be optimized by the learning agent is the following:

$$r_t = \log(1 + f_t^{speed}) - p_t^{action}$$

5.2. Agent

The learning agent is built using TF-agents' DQN implementation. The DQN agent consists of two inner layers each with 256 neurons. It makes use of the Adam optimizer and the ϵ -greedy policy ($\epsilon = 0.15$) to train. The discount factor (γ) is set to 0.85. The learning rate of the agent decays exponentially overtime. During training, the agent goes through all 12-rides step-by-step until the episode ends. The training procedure lasts for 45000 steps and the final learned policy is exported for further evaluation (Section 5.3.1). After experimenting with a variety of hyperparameters, the following were selected as the best performing ones:

- **Replay buffer size:** 10000
- **Batch size:** 256
- **Initial learning rate:** 0.001

5.3. Evaluation

We evaluate the recommendation module on a simulated environment using the previously unseen rides, and in the real-world by deploying our module on a smartphone device and collecting the feedback from a single bicyclist.

5.3.1. Simulation

To test how the recommendation module, with the learned policy in place, affects a cyclist's performance during a ride, a simulation is setup. The entire dataset is used, including the 2 previously unseen bikes that were removed from the training set during the prediction model training. During the simulation, the module offers suggestions in real-time to the cyclists regarding their BackSensor2 roll, every timestep for each individual ride. An action is sampled from the respective densities (Figure 6) according to the recommendation. At the end of each simulation, we calculate the average predicted speed and heart rate after the module recommendations have taken place and compare them to their original values for each ride.

In Table 5 we can see the average speed during each bike ride as measured by the sensors and predicted by our regression model. The close proximity of the two values shows the high accuracy of our speed prediction model. As we can see from the average speed after the suggestions, the module is able to improve the average speed of all bike rides during the simulation. Specifically, with the use of our recommendation module, the speed of each bike ride increases by **9.8 kmh on average**.

In Table 6 we can see that our heart rate regression model produces predictions close to the values measured by the sensors, proving its high accuracy and robustness. As it is evident by the average heart rate after the suggestions, the module has a minimal impact on the heart rate of each cyclist during the simulation. Specifically, with the use of our recommendation module, the heart rate of each cyclist only increases by **3.66 bpm on average**.

Since this recommendation module could potentially be used by cyclists in real-life scenarios, we need to investigate in detail what suggestions the module gives and how often. One of the main objectives for our learning agent was to limit the strain on the cyclist by suggesting increase/decrease actions only when a higher return is expected, as it was encapsulated in the reward function, making it at the same

Table 5

The average speed of each ride as it was measured and predicted before any module suggestions, as well as it was predicted after suggestions took place. The *Improvement* column is calculated based on the difference between the predicted speed with and without the module's suggestions.

Bike Rides	Average Ride Speed (kmh)			
	Measured	Predicted	After Suggestions	Improvement
1	32.65	32.62	39.17	6.55
2	31.62	31.61	40.78	9.17
3	26.88	26.83	39.76	12.93
4	32.54	32.66	42.37	9.71
5	29.64	29.75	39.41	9.66
6	36.34	36.61	38.07	1.46
7	28.74	28.57	38.33	9.76
8	32.79	32.70	41.22	8.52
9	30.34	29.93	38.83	8.90
10	27.49	27.42	41.36	13.94
11	23.93	24.08	39.45	15.37
12	30.78	30.79	39.89	9.10
13 (unseen)	29.73	28.46	39.85	11.39
14 (unseen)	31.74	28.91	39.61	10.70

Table 6

The average heart rate of each ride as it was measured and predicted before any module suggestions, as well as it was predicted after suggestions took place. The *Impact* column is calculated based on the difference between the predicted heart rate with and without the module's suggestions.

Bike Rides	Average Ride Heart Rate (bpm)			
	Measured	Predicted	After Suggestions	Impact
1	133.39	133.87	140.59	6.72
2	135.77	134.71	134.88	0.17
3	129.88	130.47	137.07	6.60
4	135.81	135.50	138.18	2.68
5	126.39	126.60	132.3	5.70
6	144.47	143.25	142.7	-0.55
7	129.24	129.59	133.82	4.23
8	136.69	136.09	135.38	-0.71
9	132.30	132.80	137.73	4.93
10	118.04	118.26	125.86	7.60
11	135.44	135.16	135.99	0.83
12	126.00	126.57	132.19	5.62
13 (unseen)	130.06	134.93	137.19	2.26
14 (unseen)	133.41	135.72	140.84	5.12

time more realistic for real-world usage. Looking at Table 7, it is clear that our recommendation module achieves exactly that, since on average around 94% of the time the Steady action is favored, and the maximum times one of the two other actions is suggested consecutively, is always less than or equal to 5. An example of how actions take place during a simulation can be seen in the timeline provided for ride #7 in Figure 7.

5.3.2. Real-world

To further evaluate our recommendation module, we needed to investigate the performance and usefulness of our model "in the wild". To achieve this, we built a demo application on an Android device (Samsung Galaxy S9) where

Table 7

Details regarding the total count and the maximum number of consecutive times each action was suggested for all rides.

Bike Rides	Action Count			Max Consecutive		
	Steady	Increase	Decrease	Steady	Increase	Decrease
1	1971	70	92	232	4	3
2	1971	53	97	198	2	4
3	1909	16	42	466	1	5
4	1902	10	42	245	1	3
5	1898	63	85	212	2	2
6	114	3	5	93	2	2
7	593	23	28	122	2	3
8	1927	93	109	165	3	3
9	642	27	47	67	1	3
10	1016	10	27	146	1	3
11	1988	4	47	158	1	2
12	2069	41	71	157	2	5
13 (unseen)	2313	22	57	268	1	3
14 (unseen)	1473	72	95	134	2	2

we deployed our recommendation module using TensorFlow Lite. The application consisted of information regarding the bicyclist's current speed, heart rate, power, position, balance, cadence and finally our module's suggestion. We then asked a single bicyclist to use this application during their bike ride (duration: 1 hour, distance: 30KM) and fill out a simple questionnaire we had prepared. The feedback we have collected is as follows:

Q: How many times did you follow the suggestions of the module? - 1: never to 5: always

A: 3

Q: Do you think the suggestions made sense (helped in improving the performance) - 1: no sense (did not help) to 5: absolute sense (always helped)

A: 2

Q: Please explain when and why you ignored the suggestions

A: "The suggestions were very frequent and sometimes I couldn't follow them. I preferred to stay in an aerodynamic position in situations where the road was flat and the suggestion was to increase my inclination."

Q: Other comments

A: "Maybe the suggestions shouldn't be so frequent, or it could be dynamic, i.e., change the frequency when some circumstances change (e.g., slope). Since the suggestions are binary, they could be in an audio form that could be easier for the cyclist to follow without having to observe the phone all the time."

As it is evident from the collected feedback, the recommendation module is not yet ready for practical real-world usage. The bicyclist did not always follow the suggestions since they either did not make sense or were too difficult to follow at times. The high frequency of suggestions and the near consecutive Increase/Decrease commands made it practically impossible for the bicyclist to execute. This observation agrees with our simulated experiments where in some cases during the ride, the recommendation module made a lot of alternating suggestions in a small timespan (e.g., Figure 7: 550-600 timesteps).

Figure 7: The timeline of actions taken after the module's real-time recommendations for bike ride #7

Before further evaluation of our recommendation module takes place in-the-wild (beyond simple bicyclist feedback), we first need to improve some practical aspects of the module, like frequency of suggestions based on environment and feasibility of the actions. Evolving the module to account for the aforementioned as well as other real-world challenges is the natural next step of this project and is left for future work.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

In our work we discussed how machine learning can be used to create a model that is able to predict a cyclist's speed, as well as other relevant target variables, with high accuracy. Specifically, we have shown that random forests, when trained using our engineered featured vector, can predict speeds with as low as 4.34 (kmh) average mean-absolute-error (MAE), under the Per Bike Ride Cross Validation method. Our prediction model also achieved an average MAE of 7.18 (bpm) for the heart rate and 3.61 (degrees) for the BackSensor1 roll target variables.

Another major contribution of this project is the creation of a recommendation module that can provide, in real-time, suggestions to the cyclists that help increase their average speed for the duration of the ride whilst having a minimal impact on their average heart rate. In Section 5 we described how this module was built, the agent that was used and the final reward function that was created through experimentation. We setup a simulation to test our module's performance, where we have shown that it is able to increase the speed of all cyclists during their rides by an average of 9.8 kmh while having only an average impact of 3.66 bpm on their heart rate. After evaluating the recommendation module in-the-wild, by deploying it on a smartphone device, and collecting feedback from a bicyclist, we discovered some issues regarding the practicality of the suggestions, mostly

circled around frequency of actions and feasibility. Further work on the module is required to address practicality issues and make it suitable for real-world usage.

Although the recommendation module presented in this work shows a lot of potential when evaluated in a simulated environment, a complete validation in the real-world is necessary to conclude whether it can provide true value to cyclists through a potential future full-scale implementation. Another challenge such a module should overcome, is that of on-the-edge deployment and continual training, where resources are limited and all data is not always available. Training online on new batches of data can cause the model to forget previously learned information (McCloskey and Cohen, 1989; Kirkpatrick et al., 2017) but such behaviour can be mitigated by using continual learning techniques (Demosthenous and Vassiliades, 2021). Doing so would enable us to refine and fine-tune both the prediction and the recommendation modules when more data become available, providing a more personalized system. Devising reward functions that encourage even sparser suggestions could potentially be achieved using longer time scales of suggestions compared to actions, and could take into account that the suggestions might not be followed by the user. The type of sensors we used do not capture air density, which could have a huge impact in air drag, and consequently affect the performance and robustness of our models. Therefore, future work should consider using more advanced sensors that take into account such important factors. Future projects should focus on creating real-world applications, building on the work that was presented in this paper, that tackle the aforementioned challenges and which cyclists could potentially use to improve their own performance.

Acknowledgements

The project was funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU, and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 739578 and the Government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

Appendices

A. Model Selection Experiments

In order to finetune the regressors we run model selection experiments, using a Per Bike Ride Cross Validation methodology, and choose the hyperparameter settings that yield the best performance for each one. Specifically, we experiment with the following hyperparameters:

- **Learning rates:** [0.01, 0.001] for GDLR, GBDT and NN
- **Estimator number:** [25, 50, 100, 200] for GBDT and RF
- **Units/Neurons:** [16, 32, 64, 128] for NN
- **Generation/Population pairs:** [(g:500, p:250), (g:1500, p:400), (g:3000, p:500), (g:6000, p:600)]

The performance of the models in terms of average MAE can be seen in Figure 9.

B. All Bike Rides Cross Validation

In the **All Bike Rides Cross Validation** method, all rides are used to create samples for the training and validation sets. Specifically, each bike ride is split into 10 blocks. 9 blocks from each ride are used to train the regression models and the remaining block is used for validation. The process is repeated 10 times each with a different block selected for validation in a round-robin fashion as seen in Figure 8. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is calculated after each iteration. The Average MAE of all iterations is used to evaluate the performance of the regression models. The training and validation sets consist of 17163 and 1907 samples respectively. This method of evaluation gives us insight on how the models would perform when at least some data from each individual ride becomes available (e.g., during retraining or personalization). We conduct model selection experiments for hyperparameter tuning using this methodology. As we can see from the results in Table 8, all regressors perform a lot better, in regard to average MAE, as expected.

References

Acikkar, M., Akay, M. F., Ozgunen, K. T., Aydin, K., and Kurdak, S. S. (2009). Support vector machines for aerobic fitness prediction of athletes. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36(2):3596–3602.

Figure 8: All Bike Rides Cross Validation

Table 8

The average mean-absolute-error of each prediction model under the All Bike Rides Cross Validation method (ranked in increasing order).

Model	Average MAE
NN (LR: 0.001, U: 128, D: 0)	3.33
RF (EST: 100)	3.35
GDLR (LR: 0.01)	3.87
GBDT (LR: 0.01, EST:200)	4.01
NLR	4.09
Symbolic Regression (gen: 6000, pop: 600)	4.59

Akay, M. F., Inan, C., Bradshaw, D. I., and George, J. D. (2009). Support vector regression and multilayer feed forward neural networks for non-exercise prediction of vo2max. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36(6):10112–10119.

Breiman, L., Friedman, J. H., Olshen, R. A., and Stone, C. J. (2017). *Classification and regression trees*. Routledge.

Chatzilygeroudis, K., Vassiliades, V., Stulp, F., Calinon, S., and Mouret, J.-B. (2019). A survey on policy search algorithms for learning robot controllers in a handful of trials. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 36(2):328–347.

Crouch, T. N., Burton, D., LaBry, Z. A., and Blair, K. B. (2017). Riding against the wind: a review of competition cycling aerodynamics. *Sports Engineering*, 20(2):81–110.

Demosthenous, G. and Vassiliades, V. (2021). Continual learning on the edge with tensorflow lite. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.01946*.

Friedman, J. H. (2002). Stochastic gradient boosting. *Computational statistics & data analysis*, 38(4):367–378.

Fujimoto, S., Hoof, H., and Meger, D. (2018). Addressing function approximation error in actor-critic methods. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 1587–1596. PMLR.

Guadarrama, S., Korattikara, A., Ramirez, O., Castro, P., Holly, E., Fishman, S., Wang, K., Gonina, E., Wu, N., Kokkiopoulou, E., Sbaiz, L., Smith, J., BartÅsk, G., Berent, J., Harris, C., Vanhoucke, V., and Brevdo, E. (2018). TF-Agents: A library for reinforcement learning in tensorflow. <https://github.com/tensorflow/agents>. [Online; accessed 25-June-2019].

Haarnoja, T., Zhou, A., Abbeel, P., and Levine, S. (2018). Soft actor-critic: Off-policy maximum entropy deep reinforcement learning with a stochastic actor. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 1861–1870. PMLR.

Heaton, J. (2016). An empirical analysis of feature engineering for predictive modeling. In *SoutheastCon 2016*, pages 1–6. IEEE.

Hessel, M., Modayil, J., Van Hasselt, H., Schaul, T., Ostrovski, G., Dabney, W., Horgan, D., Piot, B., Azar, M., and Silver, D. (2018). Rainbow: Combining improvements in deep reinforcement learning. In *Thirty-second AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*.

Hester, T. and Stone, P. (2012). Learning and using models. In *Reinforcement learning*, pages 111–141. Springer.

- Hill, T., O'Connor, M., and Remus, W. (1996). Neural network models for time series forecasts. *Management science*, 42(7):1082–1092.
- Iyer, S. R. and Sharda, R. (2009). Prediction of athletes performance using neural networks: An application in cricket team selection. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36(3):5510–5522.
- Kingma, D. P. and Ba, J. (2015). Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. In Bengio, Y. and LeCun, Y., editors, *3rd International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2015, San Diego, CA, USA, May 7-9, 2015, Conference Track Proceedings*.
- Kirkpatrick, J., Pascanu, R., Rabinowitz, N., Veness, J., Desjardins, G., Rusu, A. A., Milan, K., Quan, J., Ramalho, T., Grabska-Barwinska, A., et al. (2017). Overcoming catastrophic forgetting in neural networks. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 114(13):3521–3526.
- Koza, J. R. (1992). *Genetic Programming: On the Programming of Computers by Means of Natural Selection*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, USA.
- Li, L., Chu, W., Langford, J., and Schapire, R. E. (2010). A contextual-bandit approach to personalized news article recommendation. In *Proceedings of the 19th international conference on World wide web*, pages 661–670.
- Liakos, K. G., Busato, P., Moshou, D., Pearson, S., and Bochtis, D. (2018). Machine learning in agriculture: A review. *Sensors*, 18(8):2674.
- Liu, L., Xu, J., Liao, S. S., and Chen, H. (2014). A real-time personalized route recommendation system for self-drive tourists based on vehicle to vehicle communication. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 41(7):3409–3417.
- Liu, Y., Logan, B., Liu, N., Xu, Z., Tang, J., and Wang, Y. (2017). Deep reinforcement learning for dynamic treatment regimes on medical registry data. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Healthcare Informatics (ICHI)*, pages 380–385. IEEE.
- McCloskey, M. and Cohen, N. J. (1989). Catastrophic interference in connectionist networks: The sequential learning problem. In *Psychology of learning and motivation*, volume 24, pages 109–165. Elsevier.
- Mnih, V., Kavukcuoglu, K., Silver, D., Rusu, A. A., Veness, J., Bellemare, M. G., Graves, A., Riedmiller, M., Fidjeland, A. K., Ostrovski, G., et al. (2015). Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning. *nature*, 518(7540):529–533.
- Munguia Tapia, E. (2008). *Using machine learning for real-time activity recognition and estimation of energy expenditure*. PhD thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Orzechowski, P., La Cava, W., and Moore, J. H. (2018). Where are we now? a large benchmark study of recent symbolic regression methods. In *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference*, pages 1183–1190.
- Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., Blondel, M., Prettenhofer, P., Weiss, R., Dubourg, V., Vanderplas, J., Passos, A., Cournapeau, D., Brucher, M., Perrot, M., and Duchesnay, E. (2011). Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12:2825–2830.
- Sahin, S., Tolun, M. R., and Hassanpour, R. (2012). Hybrid expert systems: A survey of current approaches and applications. *Expert systems with applications*, 39(4):4609–4617.
- Schulman, J., Wolski, F., Dhariwal, P., Radford, A., and Klimov, O. (2017). Proximal policy optimization algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1707.06347*.
- Segal, M. R. (2004). Machine learning benchmarks and random forest regression. *UCSF: Center for Bioinformatics and Molecular Biostatistics*.
- Silver, D., Huang, A., Maddison, C. J., Guez, A., Sifre, L., Van Den Driessche, G., Schrittwieser, J., Antonoglou, I., Panneershelvam, V., Lanctot, M., et al. (2016). Mastering the game of go with deep neural networks and tree search. *nature*, 529(7587):484–489.
- Soleymani, F. and Paquet, E. (2021). Deep graph convolutional reinforcement learning for financial portfolio management–deepocket. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.08664*.
- Théate, T. and Ernst, D. (2021). An application of deep reinforcement learning to algorithmic trading. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 173:114632.
- Tsitsiklis, J. N. and Van Roy, B. (1997). An analysis of temporal-difference learning with function approximation. *IEEE transactions on automatic control*, 42(5):674–690.
- Watkins, C. J. and Dayan, P. (1992). Q-learning. *Machine Learning*, 8(3-4):279–292.
- Zheng, G., Zhang, F., Zheng, Z., Xiang, Y., Yuan, N. J., Xie, X., and Li, Z. (2018). Drn: A deep reinforcement learning framework for news recommendation. In *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference*, pages 167–176.

Deep RL for Improving Competitive Cycling Performance

Figure 9: The average mean-absolute-error of each regressor using different combinations of hyperparameters.